

**EFFECTS OF INADEQUATE EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES ON
TEACHING AND LEARNING CHALLENGES FOR ACADEMIC
EXCELLENCE.**

By

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Abstract

The thrust of this paper is that, a well planned and an integrated approach should be adopted in the development of educational resources so as to bring about Academic Excellence. It is the belief of the researcher that the establishment and utilization of educational resource centre in the schools will offer one of the best possibilities for effective teaching and learning, if well equipped and utilized. The paper therefore looked into what and how Educational Reference Centres (ERC) should be, to achieve the objectives and also conclude that each school should play a conspicuous role in the development of Educational Resource Centres (ERC) for effective academic excellence.

Key Words *ERC, CET*

Introduction

A resource is anything used to meet a need, a support, or a helping hand, while educational resources are the sum total of the input that goes into education system, in form of support for the enhancement of teaching/learning that facilitates, influence or encourage, the transmission or acquisition of knowledge, competence, skill and the know how. They are essentially, things used to aid the educational training of learners. These could be building, staff, equipments, ideas and materials i.e. it could be human and material in nature.

Educational Resource Centres

Having described educational resources as human and materials that can be used to facilitate teaching and for the acquisition of knowledge, we shall look into what Educational Resource Centres are. But first and foremost, we should understand that whether we call it Educational Resource Centre or Instructional Resources Centre or Media Centre, we are saying the same thing knowing fully that many authors, used the concept interchangeably. We can draw an inference from UNESCO survey of media centre (as reported in 1978), cited by (Agun, 1988) where its usages in English speaking countries were listed to include multi-media centre, Learning Resources Centre, Comprehensive Library, School Library/Media Centre, Learning Centre, etc. Here in Nigeria, Educational Resource Centres are called by any of the following names: Learning Resource Centre, Media Resource Centre, Centre for Educational technology, Instructional Resource Centre, Educational Media Centre etc. The difference in their names sometimes reflects the objectives of the particular centre, their activities, orientations, and the names preferred by the authorities. The underlining principles of the concepts above, could be traced to the philosophies of Cornenius in (Adekunle, 2006) in his "Schools without walls" programme where he saw the whole city/town as resources of learning materials. This gave birth to the uses of resources in teaching. (Olowu, 2005).

Resource here, includes, object of study, like books, periodicals, newspapers, pictures, diagram, maps, charts, photos, microfilms, slides, filmstrips, loop films, audio-tapes, video-tapes, zoological and botanical garden, living specimens, multimedia, metrological sites, laboratories etc. whereas, a place where all such multiplicity of items are gathered, organized and indexed for use without production

facilities, is called a resource library. But a resource centre, according to (Sampath Santhrian, 2007), must have the capacity for active creation and use of resources in order to enable an individual student to learn. The resource centres should also have the following objectives:

- i. Production of home-made resources.
- ii. Selection and acquisition of resources.
- iii. Classification and indexing for retrieval.
- iv. Storage.
- v. Uses, including guidance and
- vi. Evaluation of materials. p. 316

Types of Educational Resource Centres (ERC)

ERC varies in terms of their arrangements. It ranges from a mere classroom centre, to an entire building/complex, depending on the objective, financial ability, and the availability of both human and materials resources.

(Abimbade, 1999) identified three main types of ERC as follows;

- a. Centralized Resource Centre
- b. Decentralized Resource Centre
- c. Coordinated Resource Centre

Centralized Resource Centre

This is used for acquiring, cataloguing and storing of instructional materials. It could be in the state or local government area.

Decentralized Resource Centre

This type of centre, functions independently within a school building and it is responsible for the acquisition, cataloguing and storing of instructional materials which should be available for use by students as well as teachers.

Coordinated Resource Centre

This type of centre operates as a system and contains a network of school resource centres, but it is supplemented and served by a central resources centre which provides additional equipments and services.

Function of Educational Resource Centres (ERC)

According to (Agun, 1988)

The function of ERC could be determined by the objectives of establishing the centre and the type however, they have two common functions namely:

- i. Provision of services, materials and facilities to facilitate and enhance the achievement of educational objectives.
- ii. Servicing the teachers, in the main stream of educational development through the kind and quality of materials and services it provides.

This service is very important to keep teachers growing on the job. They need to unconditionally update their knowledge and a well structured ERC is one of the places where such growth can take place. But to be functionally useful, for the above purposes, there are some specific functions to be performed by the centre. They are:

- i. Organize workshops, seminars, in-service training and conferences for teachers on different aspects of education.
- ii. Encourage curriculum development, to includes, the planning, designing and production of different types of instructional materials.
- iii. Advise teachers and learners about proper selection and use of different type of materials. This can take the form of demonstration, discussion, direct instructions etc.
- iv. As the study and reference centres for teachers and learners. This means that the centre must have adequate educational materials which users can consult or use to obtain information.
- v. As a forum for teachers to meet and discuss professional interest and problems. pg. 60

(Abimbade, 1999) went on to list other functions that ERC should perform as follows:

- i. Identifying, acquiring, organizing and disseminating materials, information and supplies that are pertinent to the curricular.
- ii. Serving as a clearing house where teachers and students have easy access to variety of teaching and learning materials and equipments.
- iii. Giving teachers and students optimal assistance in the preparation and production of teaching and learning materials.

- iv. *Organizing microteaching* session for student-teachers in the faculty of education as well as for lecturers, to develop new teaching skills and also to revitalize already acquired ones.
- v. Planning and executing in-service training programmes for both academic and non-academic staff through seminars, workshops and conferences, as a way of updating knowledge and skills in tune with present day educational practice. pg. 120.

In this modern day of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), Educational Resource Centres should provide opportunities for training in the use of computer, multimedia and how to access the internet as well.

Materials and Equipments in the Educational Resource Centres

The materials and equipments in (ERC) could be divided into various sections/studio.

- 1) Sound/Audio Recording Studio: Tape Recorders, Editing Kits, Tape, Duplication, Audio CD Duplicator, Radio, Headphones, Blank Tapes etc.
- 2) Photographic Studio: Different types of camera, with different lenses; wide angles/telescopic etc enlargers, copy stand, film, chemicals etc.
- 3) Graphic Studio: Vanguard cards, newsprint, brown papers, plain papers, off-cuts, mechanical lettering devices, computers pen, ink, pencils of different grades, markers, airbrushes, crayon, water colour, poster colour, scissors, marking tapes, cutting knives, gum, adhesives, dry month etc.
- 4) Television Studio: Television camera, video camera, lighting equipments, video editing equipments, television monitors, cables etc.
- 5) Cinematography studio: Cine cameras, film cameras for 8mm/16mm/32mm.
- 6) Reprographic studio: Photocopying materials, ample supply of papers, stencils spirit duplications, printing machine.
- 7) Wood-workshop: Assorted saws, planes, set square, chisels, pincen, hammers, tape measure, brushes, glue etc.
- 8) Resource library: Relevant books on Radio/TV-audio/productions. Video/TV production, design, development and production of instructional materials.

- 9) Other important equipments: Different projectors-Overhead projector, opaque projector, slide, film strip, picture projector etc.
- 10) Non Projected Materials Section: Bulleting board, display board, maps, models, mockups, diarorna Realia.

Spatial Arrangements of (An Ideal) Resource Centres

(Olowu, 2005) reflected on the previous suggestion as “an effective and efficient operations within a resource centre could be determined by the aims and objectives of setting the centre as well as the function it was supposed to perform”. For instance:

- i) There should be spaces for guide and easy storage and retrievals of information.
 - ii) Adequate space should be provided for studies to accommodate both printed and non-printed materials for teaching.
 - iii) Space should be provided for viewing of audio visual and audio materials as well as recordings.
 - iv) Space for planning, designing, developing and producing materials and workshops, seminars, in-service training and conference for teachers, inspectors etc.
 - v) Spaces should be allocated for repairs and maintenance of equipments.
 - vi) Photographic studio
 - vii) Graphic / reprographic studio.
 - viii) Electronic workshop
 - ix) Mechanical workshop
 - x) A resource library. pg. 167.
- a) **Space:** - Cabins and cubicles for individual study and large group instruction. For storage and instructional materials (print and non print).
 - b) Facilities for storage and distribution of technical materials
 - c) **Space:** For production i.e. workshop for metal work, Electronics, Graphics, Photography, Audio recording room, TV production (studio), Preview of video/audio cassette, Cassette room
 - d) **Office Accommodation:** According to National Commission for Colleges of Education, Minimum Standard 2010, the Coordinator/Head of the centre/lecturers and lecturers should be, within the complex.
 - e) A-V. Technician (Room)

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- f) Film Racks
- g) Language lab
- h) Micro Teaching studio

A large cupboard for the storage of materials, tables, chairs and shelves. In addition, a computer room is hereby proposed to be incorporated into the new ERC. Many computer hardwares should be there for training/internet accessibility for the student for their on-line registrations, browsing etc.

It would be profitable for the government to establish this instead of allowing private cyber café where students could be exposed to cyber crimes.

Advantages of Educational Resources Centre

The advantages derivable from the use of ERC are numerous, examples are:

- a. Increased accessibility. It contributes immensely to the efficient, depth and variety of learning.
- b. It make information more accessible to individuals
- c. It increases the rate of comprehension of students, through the use of many sensory organs.

According to (Eshelmen, 1973) cited by (Kehinde, 2006):

“Learners retain about ten percent of what they read, twenty percent of what they hear, thirty percent of what they see. Of what they see and hear, the retention is fifty percent, of what they see as they speak, seventy percent, of what they say as they participate in activities fully ninety percent” pg. 49

- d. Through the use of ERC, interdepartmental relationship will be enhanced instead of “me and my department approach”. Every department in the College would need to liaise with the centre for one thing or the other to improve instruction and learning process.
- e. Arrangement for the use of learning aids/materials in other big halls used for lectures-like public address system (PAS) for micro classes etc.

- f. Retraining/In-service programmes for teaching/non-teaching and new members of staff.
- g. It can still serve as a training base for outsiders-skill acquisition centres etc.

Challenges Towards Academic Excellence

As far back as 1981 when the National Policy on Education was formulated by the Federal Government of Nigeria and as contained in 2004 revised edition, ERC was under Educational/Service. Objectives of educational services proposed includes:

- To develop, assess and improve educational programmes.
- To enhance teaching and improve the competence of teacher.
- To make learning more meaningful for children.
- To reduce educational cost.
- To develop and promote an effective use of innovative material in schools.

To achieve these objectives the following measures were to be taken. Item 84.1 section (10) says, Teachers Resource Centres, where teachers will meet for discussions, investigation, study, short course and conferences, will be set up in each state/local governments.

Items 4 says;

Education Resource Centres were to be established at State/Federal level. There will however, be close co-operation and constant constitution to ensure the free flow of information, in respect of achievement in this field. Item 5. Audio visual Aids Centres will be set up under the auspices of the Federal and State Governments and there will be close co-operation and constant constitution between the centres and all educational institutions for their development and effective utilization.

Other challenges are physical/structural facilities, teaching methods, faculty interest and administrators interest.

Physical/Structural Facilities -

In order to perform the functions above, (ERC)'s at tertiary institution levels should be equipped and staffed well to perform better. This is the Center for Education Technology (CET) and the likes.

What we are having in our institution now could be said to be mere shadow of the real thing, yet we would expect them to perform better. Comparing with what is on the ground and what it should be, the difference is clear. The following organogram would explain further. (This is what it should be).

Fig. 2

According to (Salisu, 1988), he was of the opinion that:

Director

↓

Technicians

(Covering the following)

- As a camera man
- Repairing
- Multimedia man
- Able hand for micro teaching recordings etc.

"Lack of adequate knowledge by administrators about learning resources has been a decisive factor in their attitude to these media and the development of learning resource centre. If the University Administrators are interested in media services, more funds will be made available for their provision. Unfortunately, in ninety institution of learning in Nigeria the administrator is at best, different and in some cases hostile to learning resources claiming that they are expensive to operate" p. 10

Fig 1. Organizational Chat of CET

Fig. 1: Source: FME Lagos committee report on Edu. Tech. May 1991

Organogram of the CET in our institution nowadays look like this

Fig. 2

The inadequacies could be felt right from here (An aberration of the real thing).

WHY IS THIS SO?

There are so many challenges confronting inadequate funding of these centres, such as;

Faculty interest:

Until the man at the helm of affairs in the Faculty of Education become interested, in the use of media and sees the need for its usages at all times during teaching and learning situation, it might be difficult to equip the centre and provide all that is required.

The centre belongs to the whole institution and should not be for the teaching of Educational Technology or Micro Teaching alone. All other faculties should make use of the centre, for instructional purposes when it is fully equipped. As it is, it is only for the related courses. Hence the poor staffing condition and infrastructure.

Administrators' Interest

The genuing interest of the administrators of the institution matters a lot in the areas of staffing and acquisition of modern hardwares/gadgets. Special budgetary allocation should be made for this purpose as specified by the NPE which says that "CET should be adequately funded to provide all that is required". But this inadequacy have been like this since.

According to (Salisu, 1988), he was of the opinion that:

"Lack of adequate knowledge by administrators about learning resources has been a decisive factor in their attitude to these media and the development of learning resource centre: if the University Administrators are interested in media services, more funds will be made available for their provision. But unfortunately, in ninny institution of learning in Nigeria the administrator is at best, different and in some cases hostile to learning resources claiming that they are expensive to operate" p. 10

A change of attitude will make the difference.

Summary and Conclusion

The development of learning resources is revealed to be, not as recent as people perceived, for it dates back to 330BC when Aristotle used the “camera obscura” as a teaching device for his student at the Lyceum. (Salisu, 1988).

Since then, various Learning Resource Centres have been developed, and in recent times computer and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) also came into the provision of Learning Resource Services in higher institution nationwide. We should note that the role of Technology in Education in the attainment of effective, efficient and resultoriented teaching and learning processes has been identified by all and sundry, and should be embraced. Since the advent of ICT, learning has acquired a radically new flavour.

According to (Northedge, 2008)

“The Information and Communication Technology (ICT) revolution, has transformed the ways in which ideas and information are recorded and communicated in the process, has brought far reaching changes to (higher) education” pg. 45

Meanwhile, computer and of course, Internet, have reconfigured the academic scene, where many universities use e-testing, for post UTME test online registration and even Computer Base Test for semester examinations.

If the Federal Government shifts the paradigm and insists that all post UTME examination should be by CBT (Computer Based Test) then we will be able to vouch for the product of our tertiary institutions. Through this, the biometric data such as finger print, iris pattern, facial shapes and vein patterns and other details of the candidate can be captured before entry and this will eliminate impersonation during examinations.

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